

Understanding perceived attributes of dietary behaviour and associated factors of nutrition status among pregnant women of Malkangiri, Odisha, India: A community based qualitative research

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Abstract

Background: Undernutrition during pregnancy is major public concern as it impacts the health of foetus and pregnant women. It is highly widespread in marginalized women in India. Hence, this study attempt to analyse the prevalence of undernutrition, its associated factor and maternal perceived attributes related to food choices to understand their eating habits throughout pregnancy.

Methods: A qualitative research was done including in-depth interviews with 104 pregnant women of Koya and Matia community women residing in five blocks of Malkangiri district, Odisha. A quantitative pre-tested open – ended questionnaire used to collect data on socio- demographic, health behaviors, reproductive factors, health habits, dietary habits and positive and negative attributes of food consumption and anthropometric measurements like height, weight and mid- upper arm circumference.

Results: The prevalence of undernutrition among pregnant women in Malkangiri district is 48.22%. Maternal age, performing household duties for long hours, substance abuse, intra-household practices, employment status, gestational month, and access to healthcare facilities were found to be significantly ($p < 0.05$) associated factors with undernutrition (MUAC <23cm).

Conclusion: Nutrition interventions such as providing nutrition education in various villages, health centers, and women's groups are crucial to ensuring optimal nutrition during pregnancy. The study suggests to promote family planning services so that women can prevent unplanned pregnancy instead of going for abortion.

Key words: Undernutrition, Associated Factors, Dietary Practice, Pregnant women, Malkangiri

Introduction

Pregnancy is a crucial time in a woman's life, with physical and hormonal changes that that increase their bodies nutritional demands to support the fetal development. Adequate calories and nutrients intake are important for placental development, safe delivery, lactation, and meeting both the maternal and foetus's nutritional needs^[1]. Maternal diet affects body mass index (BMI), maternal gestational weight gain and fetal growth, impacting the health of both expecting mother and unborn child^[1,2]. Pregnancy can also affect the future physiology and metabolism of the offspring in later life. Complications like hypertension and gestational diabetes can be caused by both undernutrition and overnutrition^[3].

Moreover, mothers who do not receive adequate nutrition or have deficiencies in micronutrients, or an imbalance in their intake of micronutrients, face a higher risk of giving birth to a baby with low birth weight^[4]. This contributes to the ongoing cycle of undernutrition^[4]. The consequences of undernutrition during pregnancy have both short-term and long-term effects on the health of the child, impacting their development throughout their lifetime^[5]. Additionally, this increases the likelihood of non-communicable diseases and is closely linked to the survival rates of both mothers and their infants. Insufficient dietary intake can lead to anemia and neural tube defects, which is a prevalent issue among marginalized women in various regions of the world^[4,5].

During the final trimester of pregnancy and infancy, there is a significant period of rapid brain development^[6]. The omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acid (PUFA) known as Docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) plays a crucial role in the functioning and development of brain, retina, skin, and heart^[6]. It is therefore essential to closely monitor the diets of pregnant and lactating women to ensure they receive sufficient amounts of long-chain omega-3 fatty acids^[6,7]. Despite the advancements made in addressing undernutrition in recent years, the issue of undernutrition during pregnancy remains a prominent public health concern in developing nations such as India. where mothers often prioritize their families' health over their own and thus putting themselves vulnerable to under nutrition. The nutritional status of women before and during pregnancy can be assessed by considering their knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions towards certain foods^[8]. Simply providing obstetric care is not enough; addressing the nutritional needs of disadvantaged women is equally important. Understanding the nutritional status of women is crucial for reducing maternal mortality and food insecurity. However, there is a lack of significant empirical research on the dietary behavior, food preferences, and factors contributing to undernutrition among pregnant women in Malkangiri, Odisha. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a study on the nutritional status of indigenous pregnant women in order to implement effective measures to address the issue. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the attributes of dietary behavior, and factors linked to undernutrition among pregnant women of Malkangiri.

The primary objective of this study was to assess the undernutrition among pregnant tribal women through mid-upper arm circumference criteria. The study also explores the factors of socio-demographic, reproductive, medical, utilization of health care to examine the association with undernutrition. Additionally, study also explore the maternal perceived attributes related to food choices to understand their eating habits throughout pregnancy.

Methods

Study design and site

A cross-sectional study was undertaken in a door-to-door household of Koyas and Matia tribal women of five blocks Maithili, Khairput, Malkangiri NAC, Korkonda, Podia of Malkangiri district of Odisha during period Nov 2021 to Oct 2022. Total 655 sample of both communities were collected in which 104 women were pregnant. A total of 104 pregnant women's in-depth interview conducted for data collection to assess the nutritional status and dietary behaviour. Twenty-three in- depth interview (IDI) held in groups of pregnant women in anganwadi center of their villages.

Ethical Approval

This study was approved by 10th Institute Ethical Committee Ref No: AUUP/IEC/AUG/2021/09 dated 15.12.2021 of Amity University, Uttar Pradesh for data collection. The study was carried out as per the Ethical guidelines issued by Institution and written informed consent was obtained from the participants and confidentiality and anonymity of the participants was ensured.

Data Collection

A convenience sampling technique was used to recruits all pregnant tribal women of both Koya and Matia community who want to be part of this study within study period. The data was collected using IDI and pretested semi-structure questionnaire used to generate data about food consumed by women during their pregnancy. Socio- demographical factors, dietary food habits and variation in diets, Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH) related behaviour, reproductive health, Medical services, utilization of health care, were included in questionnaire.

The key food list was developed based on IDI on dietary assessment and locally available food resources. The Key food list based on five criteria:

- Food available and affordable in their locality
- Food frequently they consume
- Sources of nutrient- rich diet like protein, iron, calcium, essential and good fat, vitamins
- Home stead produce or readily available
- free foraged foods seasonal availability.

For structured IDI, open- ended questions were used to generate data about food consumed by women in 24-hr recall and 7- day recall. The respondents were also asked about their dietary history and variation in diet to comprehend their daily dietary pattern. Based on the discussion on various food groups usually consumed by the women (e.g., cereals, lentils, roots, vegetables, fruits, fish, meat, egg, milk and milk products, oils). The food mentioned frequently in 24-hrs recall considered as frequently consumed foods while the food mentioned less time in 7 days recall methods considered as occasional consumed food and hardly mentioned in dietary history considered as rarely consumed foods.

In IDI women were asked about their perception, attitudes and practices on the consumption of a variety of essential foods. the interview identified these foods and inquired as to whether they were consuming them or not, the reasons for eating and not eating, the food preparation procedure and essential circumstances for consumption if the food was recommended to be consumed.

Measurements of Height, Weight, and MUAC were collected by following standard guidelines of International Society for the Advancement of Kinanthropometry (ISAK)^[9]. MUAC (in cm) measured with non- stretchable steel tape on their left arm at the midpoint between the tip of shoulder (olecranon process) and the tip of the elbow (acromion process)^[10,11] with nearest 0.1 cm reading. the questionnaire was translated into participants' local language to aid comprehension and then back translated into English by another competent person.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to describe the independent variables like socio- demographic, health medical, behaviour and reproductive variable. Qualitative data of key food list and its frequency on consumption and selection criteria and women's perception on attribute of diversified crops were tabulated. Bivariate and multivariate logistic regression was carried out to assess the undernutrition of each independent variable.

Results

Table 1 Mean and standard deviation of anthropometric measurements

Variable	Mean \pm SD
Age	25.990 \pm 6.734
Height	150.519 \pm 9.066
Weight	46.290 \pm 9.810
BMI	20.522 \pm 4.403
MUAC	21.682 \pm 2.735

Table 1 represents the anthropometric characteristics of pregnant women. Results show the mean and standard deviation of maternal age (25.990 \pm 6.734), height (150.519 \pm 9.066), weight (46.290 \pm 9.810), and MUAC (21.682 \pm 2.735).

Table 2: Socio-demographic character of study participants

Character	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Maternal Age	15-19	18	17.31
	20-29	51	49.04
	30-39	33	31.73
	40-49	2	1.92
Tribes	Koyas	57	54.81
	Matia	47	45.19
Education	Illiterate	61	58.65
	Primary	21	20.19
	Secondary and Above	22	21.15

Employed	Yes	54	51.92
	No	50	48.08
Occupation	House help	8	7.69
	Farmer	14	13.46
	Forest Collector	13	12.50
	Daily Wages	16	15.38
	SHG	3	2.88
Household Income	Below 10,000	93	89.42
	10-20k	9	8.65
	Above 20k	2	1.92
Family Size	Nuclear	52	50.00
	Joint	52	50.00
Working Household Duties Alone	Yes	36	34.62
	No	68	65.38
Substance Abuse	Yes	56	53.85
	No	48	46.15
Intrahousehold violence Practice	Yes	31	29.81
	No	73	70.19
No. of Meals Per Day	<3	69	66.35
	≥3	35	33.65
Toilet Construction	Yes	35	33.65
	No	69	66.35
Type of Drinking Water Facility	Protected	5	4.81
	Unprotected	99	95.19
Mode of Cooking	Mud Chulha	84	80.77
	Clean Fuel	20	19.23
Access to Health Care Facility within 15 km	Yes	33	31.73
	No	71	68.27
Gestation Month	First trimester	9	8.65
	Second Trimester	68	65.38
	Third Trimester	27	25.96
BMI	CED III	18	17.31
	CED II	5	4.81
	CED I	19	18.27
	Normal	37	35.58
	Overweight	25	24.04
MUAC	< 23cm	51	49.04
	≥ 23 cm	53	50.96

Table 2 depicts the socio-demographic details of the study participants. A total of 104 pregnant women were included in the study. The majority of the participants, 51 (49.04%), were within the age group of 20–29 years. Regarding educational status, 61 participants (58.65%) were illiterate. Employment status was noted in 54 participants (51.92%), while 50 participants (48.07%) were housewives. The majority of the study participants, 93 (89.42%), were from poor economic status; More than half (53.84%) of pregnant women were consuming chewing tobacco or locally made alcohol. Nearly one-fourth (29.80%) of women were facing intra-household violence frequently. More than half (66.34%) were

using open-defecation practices; either they have toilet construction but it is not functional due to a lack of water facilities or a lack of toilet installed in house premises; even 47 households were identified where toilet construction was not made. Only 19.23% of pregnant women have clean fuel facilities for cooking, and 31.73% of women have accessibility to health facilities within 15 km of their residence. Body mass index data shows that despite having pregnancy (40.38%), women had chronic energy deficiency. Overall prevalence of undernutrition among study participants was 49.03%.

Table 3 Reproductive, medical, and behavioural characteristics of participants

<i>Character</i>	<i>Variable</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Age at First Pregnancy	<18	64	61.538
	≥18	40	38.462
Gravida Group	Primi	14	13.462
	Multi Gravida	90	86.538
Parity	<3	62	59.615
	≥3	42	40.385
History of Use of Modern Family Planning	Yes	19	18.269
	No	85	81.731
Intentional Pregnancy	Not Planned/wanted	85	81.731
	Planned/wanted	19	18.269
Antenatal care followup for current Pregnancy	No used ANC care	18	17.308
	<4 times	82	78.846
	≥4 times	4	3.846
Place of ANC	Anganwadi	47	54.651
	At home by ASHA/ ANM	23	26.744
	CHC/PHC	16	18.605
Reason for not utilising ANC	Lack of Access	11	61.111
	Opposition to care	3	16.667
	Too Early in Pregnancy	4	22.222
Consumption of IFA tablet	Yes	25	24.038
	No	79	75.962
USG	Yes	39	37.500
	No	65	62.500
Taken TT injection	Yes	74	71.154
	No	30	28.846
Number of Pregnancy	1	21	20.192
	2-5	79	75.962
	≥6	4	3.846
History of Abortion/ Miscarriage in any type	Yes	43	41.346
	No	61	58.654
History of Pre-term birth	Yes	38	36.538
	No	66	63.462
History of Bleeding during current Pregnancy	Yes	27	25.962
	No	77	74.038
Received Pre- natal Dietary advice	Yes	68	65.385
	No	36	34.615
	First trimester	23	26.744

Month of Pregnancy to start antenatal care	Second trimester	58	67.442
	Third trimester	5	5.814
Any Illness During Pregnancy	Yes	25	24.038
	No	79	75.962

Table 3 shows the reproductive, medical, and behavioural characteristics of participants. Around 86.53% of women were in multi-gravida, and 40.38% of women had more than three parities. Around 81.73% of pregnancies among women were unplanned. Around three-fourths of pregnant women utilized ANC services less than four times; 67.44% of pregnant women started ANC care in their second trimester, and 24.03% of women were consuming IFA tablets regularly. Out of 104 pregnant women, 18 were not able to utilize antenatal care due to the distance, being too far from the health care facility, and having experience of before pregnancy. Data shows 41.34% of pregnant women had a history of abortion or miscarriage, while 25.92% had a history of preterm birth.

Table 4: Association of under-nutrition with socio-demographic and reproductive variables.

Character	Variable	MUAC		COR (95% CI)	p Value	AOR (95% CI)**	p Value
		<23 cm N (%)*	≥23cm N (%)*				
Maternal Age	15-19®	8 (7.69)	10 (9.61)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	20-29	16 (15.38)	35 (33.65)	1.600 [0.534 - 4.792]	0.401	1.236[0.382 - 3.998]	0.724
	30-39	26 (25)	7 (6.73)	0.300[0.090 - 1.001]	0.05	0.326 [0.094 - 1.128]	0.077
	40-49	1 (0.96)	1 (0.96)	0.800 [0.043 - 14.886]	0.881	0.402 [0.019 - 8.699]	0.561
Tribes	Koya®	36 (34.61)	21 (20.19)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	Matia	15 (14.42)	32 (30.76)	4.622 [2.017 - 10.595]	0	13.402 [3.884 - 46.245]	0
Education	Illiterate®	31 (29.8)	30 (28.84)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	Primary	7 (6.73)	14 (13.46)	2.853 [0.885 - 7.543]	0.083	3.026 [0.877 - 11.715]	0.078
	Secondary and Above	13 (12.5)	9 (8.65)	0.715 [0.267 - 1.920]	0.506	0.589 [0.202 - 1.715]	0.332
Employed	Yes®	32 (30.76)	22 (21.15)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	No	19 (18.26)	31 (29.8)	2.856 [1.171 - 5.712]	0.019	2.582 [1.168 - 5.708]	0.019
Household Income	Below 10,000®	45 (43.26)	48 (46.15)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	Above 10,000	6 (5.76)	5 (4.8)	1.125 [0.321 - 3.945]	0.854	1.411 [0.382 - 5.219]	0.606
Family Size	Nuclear®	45 (43.26)	7 (6.73)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	Joint	6 (5.76)	46 (44.23)	0.629 [0.290 - 1.364]	0.24	0.614 [0.280 - 1.346]	0.223

Working Household Duties Alone	No®	27 (25.96)	41 (39.42)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	Yes	24 (23.07)	12 (11.53)	13.034 [4.861 - 0 34.949]		11.983 [4.424 - 0 32.457]	
Substance Abuse	No®	13 (12.5)	35 (33.65)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	Yes	38 (36.53)	18 (17.3)	0.191 [0.082 - 0 0.443]		0.157 [0.063 - 0 0.387]	
Intrahousehold violence Practice	No®	29 (27.88)	44 (42.3)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	Yes	22 (21.15)	9 (8.65)	0.543 [0.248 - 0.126 1.188]		0.561 [0.294 - 0.173 1.290]	s
Toilet Construction	Yes®	17 (16.34)	18 (17.3)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	No	34 (32.69)	35 (33.65)	1.054 [0.469- 2.366]	0.899	1.064 [0.471 - 0.881 2.404]	
Mode of Cooking	Clean Fuel®	12 (11.53)	8 (7.69)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	Mud Chulha	39 (37.5)	45 (43.26)	0.814 [0.278 - 0.707 2.379]		0.816 [0.279 - 0.71 2.386]	
Access to Health Care Facility within 15 km	Yes®	7 (6.73)	26 (25)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	No	44 (42.3)	27 (25.96)	0.525 [0.229 - 0.129 1.205]		0.405 [0.164 - 0.051 1.003]	
Recent Pregnancy Planned	Wanted®	5 (4.8)	14 (13.46)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	Not Planned	46 (44.23)	39 (37.5)	0.317 [0.105 - 0.042 0.960]		0.377 [0.121 - 0.093 1.179]	
Gestation Month	First Trimester®	1 (0.96)	8 (7.69)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	Second Trimester	31 (29.8)	37 (35.57)	0.149 [0.018 - 0.08 1.259]		0.129 [0.011 - 0.099 1.470]	
	Third Trimester	19 (18.26)	8 (7.69)	0.063 [0.007 - 0.015 0.058]		0.038 [0.003 - 0.011 0.474]	
Age at Marriage	<18 years®	33 (31.73)	37 (35.57)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	>18 years	18 (17.3)	16 (15.38)	0.892[0.393- 2.025]	0.784	0.624 [0.201 - 0.415 1.938]	
Age at First Pregnancy	<18®	32 (30.76)	32 (30.76)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	≥18	17 (16.34)	21 (20.19)	1.222 [0.553 - 0.62 2.700]		1.664 [0.556 - 0.362 4.976]	
Gravida Group	Primi®	8 (7.69)	6 (5.76)	1.000[1.000-1.000]		1.000[1.000-1.000]	
	Multi Gravida	43 (41.34)	47 (45.19)	1.524 [0.489 - 0.468 4.749]		1.920 [0.593 - 0.277 6.218]	

Parity	<3 [®]	49 (47.11)	13 (12.5)	1.000[1.000- 1.000]		1.000[1.000- 1.000]	
	≥3	2 (1.92)	40 (38.46)	0.555 [0.233 - 1.322]	0.183	0.526 [0.216 - 1.280]	0.157
Antenatal care follow- up for current Pregnancy	Not used ANC care [®]	11 (10.57)	7 (6.73)	1.000[1.000- 1.000]		1.000[1.000- 1.000]	
	<4 times	36 (34.61)	46 (44.23)	2.008 [0.707 - 5.699]	0.19	1.721 [0.570 - 5.201]	0.336
	>4 times	3 (2.88)	1 (0.96)	0.524 [0.045 - 6.092]	0.605	0.427 [0.033 - 5.460]	0.513
Consumption of IFA tablet	Yes [®]	17 (16.34)	8 (7.69)	1.000[1.000- 1.000]		1.000[1.000- 1.000]	
	No	34 (32.69)	45 (43.26)	0.813[0.330 - 2.001]	0.653	0.737 [0.290 - 1.870]	0.52
BMI	CED III [®]	11 (10.57)	6 (5.76)	1.000[1.000- 1.000]		1.000[1.000- 1.000]	
	CED II	14 (13.46)	1 (0.96)	0.500 [0.045 - 5.514]	0.571	0.680 [0.057 - 8.067]	0.76
	CED I	12 (11.53)	6 (5.76)	1.167 [0.302 - 4.512]	0.823	0.885 [0.209 - 3.747]	0.869
	Normal	14 (13.46)	23 (22.11)	3.286 [1.006 - 10.735]	0.049	2.204 [0.611 - 7.955]	0.227
	Overweight	8 (7.69)	17 (16.34)	4.250 [1.169 - 15.454]	0.028	2.927 [0.699 - 12.250]	0.141

*figure in parenthesis indicate column wise percentage ** figure in parenthesis indicates 95% CI.

The analysis of dependent and independent variables in the present data was done to determine the association between undernutrition with socio-demographic factors among pregnant women (Table 4). A bivariate analysis result showed that undernutrition among pregnant women had a significant association with 20-29 years of maternal age (OR = 0.300; 95% CI 0.090 - 1.001), employment status (OR = 2.856; 95% CI 1.171 - 5.712). working household duties (OR= 13.034; 95% CI 4.861 - 34.949); substance Abuse (OR= 0.157; 95% CI 0.063 - 0.387), third trimester of gestation (OR = 0.063; 95% CI 0.007 - 0.058). However, conducting multivariate analysis on employment status (OR = 2.582; 95 % CI 1.168 - 5.708), working household duties (OR= 11.983; 95% CI 4.424 - 32.457); substance abuse (OR= 0.157; 95 % CI 0.063 - 0.387) third trimester of gestation (OR= 0.038; 95% CI 0.003 - 0.474) and access to health care facility (OR = 0.405; 95% CI 0.164 - 1.003) were found to be significant, which independently increased the risk of under-nutrition among pregnant women in Malkangiri.

Table 5: Summary of food frequency of consumed food by tribal pregnant women and its selection criteria

Key Foods	Frequency of Consuming	Cultivation in their farm/ Home Available	Seasonal	Purchasing From Local market	Target Nutrient
<i>Carbohydrate- rich foods:</i>					

Rice	1	Y	N	N	Energy
Chappati	2	N	N	Y	Energy
Potato	1	Y	N	N	Energy
Sweet Potato	2	N	N	Y	Energy
<i>Legume & Nuts</i>					
Lentil	2	N	Y	N	, Zn, K, Mn
Anchor	3	N	N	Y	Protein
Groundnut	2	N	Y	N	Protein
<i>Green Vegetables</i>					
Spinach, Bottle gourd leaves, radish leaves	2	Y	N	N	Fe, Vit C
Taro leaves	2	N	N	Y	Vit B6, C, CA
Pumpkin, Grass Pea,	2	N	N	Y	CA, Vit C
Drumstick, Bamboo curry	2	Y	N	N	Vit A, B 1, B2, B3, B6,E
Amaranth Greens leaves/ Fenugreek leaves	3	N	N	Y	Ca, K, Vit K
<i>Other Vegetables</i>					
Beans, Cauliflower, Bottle gourd	2	Y	N	N	Vit B & K, Folate, Fiber
Ash gourd	2	N	Y	N	Mn, Fiber, K, Folate, Vit B and K
Egg plant, Tomato	1	N	N	Y	Mn, Fiber, K, Folate, Vit B and K
Root crops	2	Y	N	N	fiber, Fats, Vit A
Cabbage, radish, carrot	1	Y	N	N	Vit A, Antioxidant, fiber, vit C

<i>Protein-rich animal foods</i>					
Milk/ Milk Products	3	Y	N	N	Ca
Egg	2	Y	N	N	Fe, Zn, Vit A and D
Chicken	2	Y	N	Y	Zn, Fe
Fish (bid) (rui, mrigel)	1	Y	Y	N	Fe, Zn
Fish (dried. Shutki)	1	N	Y	N	Ca
Fish (small mola, dhela)	1	Y	N	Y	Ca
<i>Fruits</i>					
Banana, Tamarind	1	Y	N	Y	Fe
Mango, Jackfruit, Black plum	3	N	Y	N	Vit A & C
Guava	2	N	Y	N	Vit C. ascorbic acid
Sapota	3	N	Y	N	Vit A & E, potassium
Pineapple, Orange, Lemon	3	N	Y	N	Vit C
Water melon, straw berries	2	N	Y		Electrolytes and mineral

* ref (1= frequently, 2= occasionally, 3= rarely; Y= Yes, N= No)

Attributes of Diversified food groups

During IDI, study found that women choice for their food depend on the perception of attributes either positive or negative about food. Mostly women reported that their food choice and its consumption depend upon the availability of food, affordability, health belief and cultural norms about food.

Participants responded that animal food like egg, meat, milk and milk products are also source of their income. and they are also aware that these foods are nutrients rich and help in foetal development. A pregnant women said,

“I took animal food in her second trimester but now reduce the consumption in third trimester so the fetal will be small size and if emergency arise and i will not be able to go health center then i can give birth at home easily.”

However, some women reported that animal meat causing them indigestion and diarrhoea and dislike the smell during cooking. In Addition, few women belief that pig, duck and goat meat can lead to miscarriage and still birth. Their community traditional healer *Disari*, advised them to stop the consumption of these animal meat during pregnancy and lactation.

Study also found that women are more accepting vegetable nutrients as it is easily available and offer a variety of preparation and consumption options. Mostly women perceived that leafy vegetable, green vegetable, fruits were nutritious and beneficial for both mother and children. However, few reported that jackfruit, peas, lima bean, egg plant are causing bloating and gastric, even amaranth leaves that recommended by health care which is rich in vitamin A and C, and iron causing throat itching and bloating, gastric.

‘A women stated the recipe to consume the amaranth leaves and make it more palatable by adding dry fishes while cooking and make it tastier.’

Women responded they rarely consume fruits since fruit are imported and costly, their family cannot afford variety of fruit they consume banana, guava, papaya, watermelon seasonally which is available in their house at that season. A pregnant women said,

” My child has been eaten banana and, in this season, only a single banana will produce fruits, this banana is also source of income for us. If i eat, my child cannot eat, I only eat fruit when we have enough amount of fruit but we cannot even provide it to give to the child always’

The study found that tribal women mostly consumed pakhala; recipe of fermented rice that has a soothing effects on the body and aids digestion due to its high concentration of healthy bacteria for the gut, which improves colon health and aids in smooth bowel movement. It contain modest amount of carbohydrate, fat and protein for instance 120 grams of pakhala contain 46 kcal, 7.5 g carbohydrate, 1.3 g fat and 1.1 g protein and high on micronutrients and minerals such as iron, potassium and calcium.

Table 6: Diversified food groups and mother’s positive and negative perception on attributes of food group through IDI.

Food groups	Positive attributes	Negative attributes	How to prepare	Under what condition women consume food groups
Rice	Staple recipe	Not liking taste	Pakhala	Family Affordability
	Easily Available		White rice	Access at home
	Satisfy their hunger		Fried Rice/ Biryani	
Milk/ milk products	Good for child health	Too expensive	Cow milk to drink	Advised by doctor
		Can sale and earn money	Making Dishes with Milk	Cattles at home
		Prefer to give the children	Curd	
Egg	Nutrition	Dislike the taste	Boiled	Awareness through anganwadi center
	Good for Health	Having bad smell		Family Affordability
	Supplied by Anganwadi	Prefer to give it to children	Omelette	Access at home

	Easier and quicker to prepare		Egg curry	Homestead poultry produce
Fish/ meat	Easily available	Meat is expensive	Fish curry with vegetables	Fish is easy to catch
	Nutrition	No market access for women	Fried fish	Fish can be afford by family easily
	Fish is Staple food	Dislike smell of fish	Chicken biryani	Access at home
	Like taste of Fish/ Meat		Chicken	Available in local market
Fruits	Good for Health	Few fruits avoid in pregnancy	Available in their garden	Expensive/ imported family rarely buy from local market
	Nutritious	Expensive	Eat fresh	Having tree in their garden
	Appetizer	Cause gastric/ constipation		Banana easily available
	Like to eat			Provided by Anganwadi center
Green Vegetables and other vegetable	Available in their field	Food taboo	Curry with dry fish	Home produce
	Nutritious	Cause cold and acidity problem	Vegetable curry	Seasonal Available
		Avoid so foetus will be small size, and home birth will be easier for them	Daal maa	Access at home
		Few vegetables cause indigestion and bloating		Available at local market in reasonable price
Whole grain/ Legumes	Nutritious	Considered as cold food	Khichdi	Family can afford
	Good for Pregnancy	Dietary restriction	Daal	Locally Produce
	Reduce Vomiting	Not easily available		Available in season

Discussion

The current study is designed to focus on the status of undernutrition using MUAC, which shows that 49.03% of pregnant women were undernourished while 50.96% of pregnant women had normal nutrition. This study's findings are different from a previously conducted study in Northern Maharashtra^[11], which showed that 21.8% of pregnant women were undernourished. This variation may stem from the relatively improved socio-economic conditions in Northern Maharashtra^[11] compared to the districts in Southern Odisha. Additionally, infrastructure and healthcare services are likely more readily available in Maharashtra than in the severely impacted Maoist districts of Odisha's Malkangiri, which lies in the Red Belt region.

The findings in the present study of undernutrition among pregnant women is also higher than community-based research conducted in rural Ethiopia^[12] was 39.94% (95% CI 34.7- 45.2). The data from NFHS-5 (2019-20) shows 74.3% pregnant women in Malkangiri were anemic^[13]. The main reason behind the high anemic condition in the study area was poor intake of an iron-rich diet, low socio-economic conditions, high malaria cases, and so on. The major predictor of current study are maternal age, employment status, working household duties, substance abuse, gestation month, and access to health care facilities, all of which were found to be linked with undernutrition. A study conducted in Tigray, Northern Ethiopia, ^[14] showed pregnant women whose occupation was agriculture were more likely (AOR= 2.6; 95% CI 1.5, 4.5) to have undernutrition compared to their counterparts. Variables associated with adjusted analysis indicated that women who had planned pregnancy were less likely (AOR= 0.25; 95% CI 0.14, 0.448) to be undernutrition as compared to those who had unplanned pregnancy. Mothers who did not have malaria infection during pregnancy were also less likely (AOR= 0.291; 95% CI 0.152, 0.555) to become undernourished than their counterparts. Conversely, mothers with hemoglobin below 11 g/dl were more likely (AOR= 4.9; 95% CI 3.09, 7.8) to be undernourished than their counterparts.

This study's results are comparable with the results of nutritional status of childbearing mothers in Bangladesh^[15]. Both study findings indicate poor- economic conditions, illiteracy, large family size, early age of marriage, age at first delivery, low BMI and lack of healthcare facilities. Our study findings show Matia tribe women had higher odds of experiencing undernutrition compared to Koya pregnant women. This difference may be attributed to several factors. Koya, as the dominant tribe in Malkangiri, reside in nearby town areas and generally have better educational status and dietary knowledge than Matia tribal women, who predominantly live in the interior geographical areas of the district. the key findings of this study consumption of diversified food and factors influencing in accessibility and affordability. the study also documented that the seasonal variation also affects the fruit and vegetable variation that influence food security and dietary diversity^[16,17,18]. Overall, Undernutrition among pregnant women is nearly fifty percent, attributable to various factors such as food taboos, social norms, health belief cultivation of low-nutritional crops, and consuming gutka, paan, tendu leaves, local beverages, and consumption of insufficient food intake than average diet^[17]. Additionally, few women mentioned that they abstained from consuming eggs and sattu, despite these being distributed to them by the government through anganwadi workers for their better health, due to a dislike for their taste for it. During study, it was found that low intake of Iron and Folic Acid (IFA) ^[16]supplements is attributed to the taboo surrounding medicine consumption during pregnancy, as they believe it leads to birth defects in children. Despite government interventions aimed at improving maternal health status, it was observed that both tribes rely more on traditional healthcare practices and facilitators such as *Disari*, rather than modern health infrastructure.

The study findings show there is a significant relationship between the working household duties alone and nutritional status ($p < 0.05$). We observed that pregnant women often engage in long hours of household chores and collecting wood for cooking. Additionally, we found that women who planned their current pregnancy are less likely to experience undernutrition compared to those with unplanned pregnancies, a trend consistent with studies conducted on Northwest Ethiopia by Kumera et al. and Mariyam et al^[19].

The high parity among Indian women tends to deplete their nutritional status, as the stress of pregnancy and lactation is not adequately compensated for by dietary intake[20]. Furthermore, our study revealed that women who attend antenatal care (ANC) check-ups more than four times and following nutrients recommendations of ANC are less likely to experience undernutrition compared to those who do not attend ANC check-ups, indicating that better access to healthcare facilities contributes to improved nutritional status^[21-23].

Conclusion

In this study, the prevalence of undernutrition among pregnant women in Malkangiri district is 48.22%. Maternal age, performing household duties for long hours, substance abuse, intra-household practices, employment status, gestational month, and access to healthcare facilities were found to be significantly associated factors with undernutrition (MUAC <23cm). Other socio-demographic factors and reproductive characteristics were not identified as predictors of undernutrition in pregnant women. Thus, nutrition interventions such as providing nutrition education in various villages, health centers, health posts, and women's groups are crucial to ensuring optimal nutrition during pregnancy

Recommendations

Proper nutrition is vital during pregnancy to monitor the effective credible systems for documenting the meals and nutrients including dietary supplements that women take during pregnancies. Further research and awareness programs are needed on the indigenous women of this geographical region to create effective guidelines for preventing malnutrition in pregnant women. Nutritional education should be integrated into maternity care through information, education and communication (IEC) activities. The present study also recommends to educate and aware the importance of nutrition to the caregiver of pregnant women i.e elderly women, family members or husband. It is also recommended to promote family planning services so that women can avoid unwanted pregnancy instead of going for abortion. To address the women nutrition issue, it is important to promote rural livelihood, empowering women socially, economically, and expand women's education should be implemented in tribal region.

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